

NOTES

Some Semicarbazone Derivatives of Diorganotin(IV)

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SOME semicarbazone derivatives of diorganotin(IV) of 1:1 mole ratio have been prepared and characterised. Their structures have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, conductance ir and ^1H nmr spectral data.

The donor ability of several semicarbazones derived from aldehydes and ketones towards transition and non-transition metals has been studied¹⁻⁵ but their interaction with organometallic derivatives has not been examined. The paper reports the preparation and characterisation of semicarbazones derivatives of a few diorganotin(IV) moieties.

Experimental

Ph_2SnCl_2 was prepared as reported earlier⁶. Bu_2SnO (Aldrich, USA) was used without further purification. The semicarbazones (Fig. 1) were prepared by the standard method⁷. All reactions were carried out under anhydrous conditions in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Fig. 1. $[\text{H}_2\text{L}-1]\text{R}_1=\text{H}, \text{R}_2$; $[\text{H}_2\text{L}-2]\text{R}_1=\text{H}, \text{R}_2=\text{OH}$,
 $[\text{H}_2\text{L}-3]\text{R}_1=5, 6\text{-Benzo}, \text{R}_2=\text{H}$.

Preparation of organotin(IV) complexes :

Bu_2SnL : Bu_2SnO (5 mmol) and ligand (5 mmol) were mixed in anhydrous benzene (35 ml). The contents were refluxed over a fractionating column for ~ 20 h at $\sim 120^\circ$. The azeotrope was collected at 80° . The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product washed with n-hexane and dried in vacuum.

Ph_2SnL : A solution of semicarbazone ($\text{H}_2\text{L}=\text{salicylaldehyde semicarbazone}$; 5 mmol) in anhydrous methanol (10 ml) was added under stirring to a freshly prepared solution of sodium methoxide (obtained from 5 mmol sodium metal and 25 ml anhydrous methanol). The mixture was stirred for 1 h to obtain sodium salt of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone. The excess methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the salt was suspended in benzene (50 ml). To it was added dropwise a solution of Ph_2SnCl_2 (5 mmol) in benzene (25 ml) under refluxing condition and the mixture was further refluxed for 4 h. The mixture was then filtered and the excess solvent distilled off under reduced pressure. The product when allowed to stay in deep-freeze, yielded a crystalline solid which was washed with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to 1:1 stoichiometry with the ligands present in their dianionic form. The complexes are yellow solid with sharp melting point. They are stable towards atmospheric oxygen and moisture. The molar conductance in DMF lies below $10 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA FOR R_2SnL COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	R	L	M.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molecular weight
				C	H	N	Sn	
1.	Ph	L-1	152	50.80 (53.87)	3.70 (3.78)	9.80 (9.34)	26.42 (26.39)	500.1 (449.7)
2.	Bu	L-1	105	46.75 (46.86)	6.10 (6.10)	10.80 (10.25)	29.04 (28.97)	420.8 (409.7)
3.	Ph	L-2	140	54.28 (54.34)	4.00 (4.09)	9.00 (9.05)	25.70 (25.59)	475.5 (463.7)
4.	Bu	L-2	90	48.22 (48.15)	6.40 (6.37)	9.82 (9.91)	28.00 (28.01)	415.4 (423.7)
5.	Ph	L-3	260	57.50 (57.68)	3.75 (3.80)	8.50 (8.40)	24.02 (23.75)	520.8 (499.7)
6.	Bu	L-3	155	52.10 (52.20)	5.75 (5.87)	9.10 (9.13)	25.80 (25.82)	470.6 (459.7)

Semicarbazones exhibit a broad band in the region $3150-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (H bonded OH) in their ir spectra. The disappearance of this band in the corresponding organotin complexes is indicative of deprotonation of both the protons of the semicarbazones and their subsequent participation in chelation. The band at 3440 cm^{-1} is assigned to NH_2 stretching mode which does not change on complexation, indicating its non-involvement in coordination. A strong band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in all the ligands due to azomethine group exhibits splitting on complexation, having one band located almost at the original position $1600 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to uncoordinated azomethine and the other shifted to lower frequency at $1585 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ arising from the coordinated $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ mode. The splitting of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ suggests that only one of the azomethine nitrogens is involved in coordination⁶. Several new bands at 570 ± 5 , 370 ± 5 , 270 ± 5 and at $235 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}^{\ominus}}$, $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{N}^{\ominus}}$, $\nu_{\text{asym Sn}-\text{Ph}}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym Sn}-\text{Ph}^{\oplus}}$, respectively.

The ^1H nmr spectra of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone and the complex were recorded in deuterated chloroform. In the spectrum of the complex, the peak due to OH protons disappears, which indicates deprotonation of the ligand. The signal for the azomethine proton in the salicylaldehyde semicarbazone at $\delta 8.50$ shifts towards higher field at $\delta 8.68$, indicating donation of lone-pair of electron to the central metal atom. Two groups of quadruplet and triplet observed at $\delta 7.67$ and 7.08 are attributed to the phenyl protons of ligand and Lewis acid, respectively. The structure of the complexes is tentatively assigned as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Structure of the complex: $\text{R}' = \text{Ph, Bu}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H} = \text{R}_2$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_1 = 6,6\text{-Benzo}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$.

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References

1. H. J. FORSBERG, *Coord Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **10**, 195.
2. S. P. MITAL, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 199.

3. R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 602.
4. B. B. MAHAPATRA and S. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 526.
5. L. BHAL, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 951.
6. T. HARADA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1926, **4**, 266.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1956, p. 344.
8. R. SINGH, J. P. SRIVASTAVA and L. K. MISRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 805.
9. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and A. K. S. CHAUHAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 371.
10. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967.
11. T. TANAKA M. KOMURA, Y. KAWASAKI and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1966, **1**, 484.

Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *N*-(8-Aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)-ethylenediamine and -propylenediamine Schiff Bases

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COUMARIN and its derivatives have been found to exhibit physiological activity and are also extensively used as analytical reagents^{1,2}. 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has been found to exhibit anticoagulant and plant growth regulant property^{3,4}. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with the Schiff bases *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)ethylenediamine (AHCE) and *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)propylenediamine (AHCP).

Experimental

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (AHC) was prepared by literature procedure⁵. The diamines (ethylenediamine and propylenediamine) were of B.D.H. quality. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The Schiff bases AHCE (m.p. 131.5°) and AHCP (m.p. 146°) were synthesised by refluxing AHC and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry ethanol medium for 30 min, and the yellow crystals separated on cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The metal chelates were prepared by refluxing the aqueous ethanolic solutions of the respective metal(II) chlorides (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) for 2-3 h on a water-bath. pH of the solution was adjusted to ~ 7 by dropwise addition of 10% sodium acetate solution. The precipitated metal

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